

A COMPREHENSIVE REVIEW OF ANALYTICAL METHODS FOR THE DETERMINATION OF UPADACITINIB HEMIHYDRATE IN ULCERATIVE COLITIS THERAPY

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ABSTRACT

Upadacitinib hemihydrate is a selective Janus kinase-1 (JAK1) inhibitor approved for the treatment of immune-mediated inflammatory diseases, including ulcerative colitis. Due to its oral administration, favorable pharmacokinetics, and targeted action, it is an effective option for patients with moderate to severe disease. Reliable analytical methods are essential for its quality control, stability testing, pharmacokinetic studies, and therapeutic monitoring in bulk drugs, dosage forms, and biological samples. This review summarizes its key properties and highlights reported analytical techniques—mainly HPLC, UPLC, and LC-MS/MS—emphasizing the need for sensitive and validated methods for routine and stability analysis.

KEYWORDS: Ulcerative Colitis, Upadacitinib Hemihydrate, JAK1 Inhibitor, Pharmacokinetics, Analytical Method.

INTRODUCTION

Introduction of Ulcerative Colitis

Ulcerative colitis (UC) is a chronic inflammatory bowel disease characterized by continuous inflammation and ulceration of the colon and rectum, beginning in the rectum and extending proximally. It is considered an autoimmune condition resulting from genetic, immune, and environmental factors. Common symptoms include abdominal pain, bloody diarrhea, fatigue,

and weight loss. Treatment aims to reduce inflammation, maintain remission, and prevent relapse using amino salicylates, corticosteroids, immunosuppressants, and JAK inhibitors such as upadacitinib.^[1]

Introduction of Upadacitinib Hemihydrate

Upadacitinib is an orally administered advanced therapy approved for the treatment of moderate to severe ulcerative colitis in adults. Clinical studies have demonstrated its efficacy in inducing clinical remission and improving endoscopic outcomes, including in patients with prior inadequate response to conventional or biologic therapies. Evidence from pivotal clinical trials supports its role as an effective treatment option with an acceptable safety and tolerability profile. Owing to its oral administration and demonstrated clinical benefits, upadacitinib represents a valuable addition to the therapeutic options available for the management of ulcerative colitis.^[2]

History of Upadacitinib Hemihydrate

The U.S. Food and Drug Administration (FDA) granted approval to upadacitinib in August 2019 for the treatment of adults with active rheumatoid arthritis. Subsequently, it has also been approved for psoriatic arthritis, atopic dermatitis, ulcerative colitis, and ankylosing spondylitis.^[3] In December 2019, the European Commission and Health Canada extended approvals,^[4,5] and more recently, indications have expanded to include giant cell arteritis in adults and active polyarticular juvenile idiopathic arthritis in children ≥ 2 years of age. The drug is marketed under the brand name RINVOQ®.^[3]

From a formulation perspective, upadacitinib is available as a hemihydrate salt, which improves its physicochemical stability and contributes to favorable pharmacokinetic properties, including bioavailability. Its development is regarded as a significant advancement in the field of targeted immunomodulation for immune-mediated inflammatory diseases.^[5]

Mechanism of action

Upadacitinib is a highly selective Janus kinase-1 (JAK1) inhibitor developed to specifically interfere with cytokine-mediated signaling pathways that play a central role in inflammation, immune system regulation, and disease progression. By selectively blocking JAK1 activity, it influences multiple biological processes, including cytokine and interferon signaling, lipid metabolism, and hematopoiesis. Unlike non-selective JAK inhibitors that target JAK1, JAK2, and JAK3 simultaneously, selective inhibition of JAK1 was intended to minimize adverse

effects such as cytopenias and other off-target toxicities. Nevertheless, ongoing clinical studies and real-world evidence are still evaluating whether this theoretical selectivity translates into significant clinical benefits.^[6]

Fig. 1: Mechanism of action Pharmacokinetics of Upadacitinib Hemihydrate.

Absorption: Upadacitinib Hemihydrate exhibits a dose-proportional pharmacokinetic behavior within its therapeutic range. After oral administration, the drug is rapidly absorbed, and the median time to achieve peak plasma concentration (T_{max}) is typically between 2 to 4 hours. Steady-state plasma levels are attained within approximately 4 days of once-daily dosing, showing minimal drug accumulation. Administration with food does not produce any clinically meaningful changes in key pharmacokinetic parameters such as AUC, C_{max} , or C_{min} for the extended-release formulation.

Distribution: In patients with rheumatoid arthritis (~74 kg), the apparent volume of distribution of upadacitinib hemihydrate after oral administration of the extended-release formulation is ~224 L, while in healthy subjects, the steady-state distribution volume is ~294 L. The drug distributes evenly between plasma and blood cells.

Metabolism: Upadacitinib hemihydrate is primarily metabolized via CYP3A4, with minor CYP2D6 involvement, and produces no pharmacologically active metabolites. In radiolabelled studies, ~79% of plasma radioactivity was unchanged drug and ~13% was the main metabolite from mono-oxidation and glucuronidation.

Excretion: occurs through feces (~38% unchanged) and urine (~24% metabolites). Plasma levels may be affected by CYP3A4 modulators, with inhibitors increasing and inducers

decreasing drug exposure. Overall, ~34% of the total dose is eliminated as metabolites.

Dosing: the normal dose of Upadacitinib Hemihydrate is 15 Mg.^[7]

Side effect of drug

Common Adverse Effects: Nausea, headache, acne, cough, and fever.

Serious Adverse Effects: Increased risk of severe infections (e.g., tuberculosis, herpes zoster), malignancies including certain cancers, and hypersensitivity reactions such as rash and anaphylaxis.^[7]

Drug Profile

Chemistry of Upadacitinib Hemihydrate is (3S,4R)-3-ethyl-4-(3H-imidazo[1,2a]pyrrolo[2,3-e]pyrazin-8-yl)-N-(2,2,2-trifluoroethyl)pyrrolidine-1-carboxamide Hemihydrate (fig.2) its Molecular Formula is C₁₇ H₂₁ F₃ N₆ O₂ it is novel molecule with molecular weight 398.39 g/mol. The partition co-efficient (log P) is 2.57 The appearance is white to off – white crystalline powder and the melting point is 152-156 °C Sparingly soluble in water, soluble in DMSO, Methanol. A 15mg dose is prescribed orally once a day.^[7]

Fig 2: Structure of Upadacitinib Hemihydrate.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

Reported Methods For estimation of Upadacitinib Hemihydrated.

Sr.No	Title	Description	Ref.No
1	Quantification of an anti-rheumatic agent Upadacitinib in biological Fluid (plasma) by LC-MS/MS	Stationary phase: C18 column (150 × 4.6 mm, 3.5 μm) Mobile Phase: Acetonitril : water (50:50 % v/v) Retention time(min): 3.12 min Flow rate: 1 mL/min Wavelength: 262nm Linearity: 12.5-100 ng/mL	8

2	Development of an UPLC – MS/MS method for the quantitative analysis of Upadacitinib in beagle dog plasma and pharma cokinetics study	Stationary phase: C18 column (50×2.1 mm,1.7 μm) Mobile phase: Acetonitrile : 0.1% formic acid in water (10:90 % v/v) Flow rate: 0.40 mL/min Linearity : 1-500 ng/mL	9
3	A UPLC Method Development and Validation Study of Upadacitinib and its impurities in Extended-Release Oral Tablet Dosage Forms	Stationary phase: C18 column(50×2.1mm,1.7 μm) mobile phase: Acetonitrile: methanol : 0.1% tri fluoro acetic acid (50:20:30 % v/v/v) Flow rate: 0.2 mL/min Retention time(min): 2.289 min Linearity : 15.0-180.0 μg/mL Wavelength: 231.2nm	10
4	Validation of LC-MS/MS for Monitoring of Upadacitinib in Rat Plasma Samples	Stationary phase: C18 column(150×4.6mm,5μm) Mobile phase: 0.1% formic acid: Acetonitrile (20:80%v/v) Flow rate: 0.6 mL/min Retention time(min): 1.65±0.05 min Linearity : 10.0-500.0 ng/mL	11
5	To develop and validate a Multiplex HPLC-MS/MS assay for the monitiring of JAK inhibitors in patient plasma	Stationary phase: C18 column (150×2.1 mm,2.5 μm) Mobile phase: 0.1% Formic acid : acetonitrile (20:80 % v/v) Flow rate: 0.3 mL/min Retention time(min): 1.5 min Linearity : 1-400 ng/mL	12
6	Development and Validation of a sensitive LC-MS/MS assay for determination of Upadacitinib in Human plasma and its application in patients with inflammatory bowel disease	Stationary phase: C18 column (100 ×4.6 mm,2.5 μm) Mobile phase: 0.1% formic acid: acetonitrile (35:65 % v/v) Flow rate: 40 mL/min Linearity : 0.5-200 ng/mL	13
7	A Liquid Chromatographic Method For The Reliable Quantification of Upadacitinib And Its Specified Impurities	Stationary Phase: Waters × Bridges C18 column (250 ×4.6 mm,5μm) Mobile Phase: Formic acid: methanol (60:40 % v/v) Flow Rate: 1.0 mL/min Wavelength: 256nm Linearity: 75-450 μg/mL	14
8	Analytical Quality by Design for Chiral Pharmaceuticals: A Robust	Stationary phase: Chiralpak AD-H (250 × 4.6 mm,5μm)	15

	HPLC Method For Upadacitinib Enantiomeric Quantification	Mobile phase: n- hexane:ethanol mixture (70:30 % v/v) Flow rate: 1.8 mL/min Wavelength : 230nm Linearity: 5-50 µg/mL	
9	Related Substance method development and validation of Upadacitinib Using RP-HPLC and its Degradation products	Stationary phase: Symmetry ODS C18 column (250× 4.6 mm,5µm) Mobile Phase:	16
	were characterized by Using LC-MS/MS	Acetonitrile: Methanol (80:20 % v/v) Flow rate: 1.0 mL/min Wavelength: 272 nm Linearity: 75-450 µg/mL	
10	Separation and characterization of degradation impurities of Upadacitinib by liquid Chromatography and high resolution mass spectrometry	Stationary phase: C18 column(250× 4.6 mm,5 µm) Mobile phase: Ammonium formate: Acetonitrile (60:40 % v/v) Flow rate: 0.4-1.0 mL/min Wavelength: 254 nm Linearity: 15-12 µg/mL	17

CONCLUSION

Upadacitinib hemihydrate represents a significant advancement in the management of ulcerative colitis due to its selective JAK1 inhibition, proven clinical efficacy, and acceptable safety profile. Its well-defined pharmacokinetic and physicochemical characteristics support its use as an orally administered targeted immunotherapy. The literature review clearly indicates that a wide range of analytical methods, particularly HPLC and LC-MS/MS techniques, have been successfully developed and validated for the quantification of upadacitinib in pharmaceutical formulations and biological samples. These methods demonstrate high sensitivity, precision, and reproducibility, making them suitable for routine quality control, pharmacokinetic studies, and stability assessment. Overall, this review provides a consolidated overview of existing analytical methodologies for upadacitinib hemihydrate and serves as a useful reference for researchers and analysts involved in method development, validation, and regulatory evaluation of this drug.

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